

ABSTRACT BOOK

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Improved Cryopreservation of Chicken Gonadal Germ Cells via Vitrification

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Although oocyte and embryo cryopreservation in chickens remains unfeasible, preserving embryonic gonads provides a promising alternative. Gonadal germ cells (GGCs) within embryonic gonads can develop into functional sperm or eggs. When injected into sterile 2.5-day-old embryos, cryopreserved GGCs can colonize recipient gonads and produce donor-derived gametes. However, freeze/thaw damage prolongs the in vitro culture of cryopreserved GGCs compared to fresh cells, emphasizing the need to improve gonad cryopreservation. This study presents a vitrification protocol that preserves functional GGCs and improves derivation rates (DR) compared to slow-freezing with STEM-CELLBANKER.

Gonads from 9- to 10-day-old GFP+ embryos were used. For slow freezing, 9 gonads were frozen and thawed following Hu et al. (2022, 2024). For vitrification, 24 gonads were loaded into acupuncture needles, sequentially exposed to two chilled cryoprotectant solutions (Solution 1: 7.5% DMSO, 7.5% ethylene glycol; Solution 2: 15% DMSO, 15% ethylene glycol, 0.5 M sucrose), 5 minutes each, then immersed in liquid nitrogen. Thawing involved three steps at 37 °C in decreasing sucrose concentrations (1 M, 0.5 M, 0.25 M). Gonads were cultured individually for three weeks; cultures with ~50,000 GGCs or more were considered successful. DR was calculated as (successful cultures / total cultures) × 100. One culture was used to inject fifteen 2.5-day-old non-GFP embryos with ~5000 GGCs each, assessing gonadal colonization after 7 days.

Vitrification yielded higher ($p < 0.01$) DR (58.3%) and average GGCs/gonad (9.9×10^4) compared to SCB (0% and 7.6×10^3). DRs were higher ($p < 0.05$) for vitrified testes (66.7% vs. 0%) and left ovaries (62.5% vs. 0%), with no difference for right ovaries. Left ovaries showed an increase ($p < 0.05$) in GGC yield (1.4×10^5 vs. 5.7×10^3). Among embryos surviving GGC injection (10/15), 80% showed successful gonadal colonization.

In conclusion, we propose a vitrification protocol that improves GGC derivation and offers an alternative to slow-freezing with STEM-CELLBANKER.

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References:

Tuanjun Hu et al. 2022, eLife,11, e74036; Tuanjun Hu et al.,2024, Poultry Science, 103, 1-9.